

LASER4SURF

Laser for Mass Production of
functionalised metallic surfaces

DELIVERABLE D8.5

Introductory Project Video

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VERSION CONTROL

Version	Date	Contributors	Sections Affected
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2			

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project is expected to produce an introductory project video within the first four months of the project. The LASER4SURF introductory video is intended as a general presentation tool to be shown on the LASER4SURF website, at fairs, conferences or other relevant events and upon request. Targets for distribution are researchers and stakeholders at large. The LASER4SURF introductory video is aimed at informing relevant stakeholder communities of the general purpose of the project, its objectives, technologies used, targets and expected impacts deliverable.

The LASER4SURF introductory video is set up along the details of subtask 8.2.3 (creation of original content) described in work plan table of Annex 1 “Description of the Action” of the Grant Agreement.

THE VIDEO PRODUCTION PROCESS

The video has been created by ESCI. As it was not possible to film anything on the design process and prototype production in the first months of the project, the video has used existing footage of the facilities, acquired footage and created some own animations to explain the technology of the process. For this video, ESCI has used the standard procedure of professional video production. The production process was divided in five parts:

1. Conceptual phase

First, the concept of the video was produced in writing and discussed internally at ESCI. Here, the producer provided a provisional voice-over text and suggested video footage and a possible video animation that had to be produced. The concept indicated, that the final film would be less than three minutes long.

2. Footage Search

For the bulk of video material, ESCI relied on using existing video footage. The LASER4SURF partners were asked if they had suitable video material of their facilities that could be used for the LASER4SURF video. In addition, stock footage libraries like pond5.com were used to find and license additional video footage to tell the LASER4SURF story.

3. Animation

For the animation, the producer created a 2D animation to visualize a slow motion of how the ultrashort pulse laser processes a metal surface. In addition, the logo of Laser4surf was animated to be used in this video and

4. Editing + Finalizing

On January 28th - 30th 2018 the video was edited based on the script and video material collected. The first edit of the film was approved by all partners in the following days. After their approval, the video material and music were licensed, and a professional voice-over artist provided the final voice recording for the video.

5. Presentation + Adjustments

The video was launched on the LASER4SURF YouTube channel on 6th February 2018 and can be viewed on the following URL:

<https://youtu.be/UJIGwnpclSq>